

Translational Research: Leveraging Spatial Behavior and Longitudinal Activity Space Data for Advancing Mobile Health (mHealth) Interventions

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Abstract

Translational spatial information theory research can improve public health through the incorporation of geographic principles into health interventions. This research presents a novel approach for 1) leveraging spatial behavior as a treatment target to advance behavioral mobile health (mHealth) interventions, and 2) capturing and modeling individual activity space and environmental exposure data to investigate mHealth intervention efficacy. This approach is demonstrated in the context of a randomized controlled trial of the mHealth intervention PNC-txt (Peer Network Counseling-text), which focuses on social and spatial behaviors as a treatment target, as applied to reducing problematic cannabis use among a sample of over 1,000 young adults with cannabis use disorder (CUD) in the U.S. states Colorado and Tennessee. Survey instruments on each subject's activity space locations, perceived close friends, and which close friends spend time with the subject at each activity space location, are delivered at baseline, 1 month (at the completion of the intervention), 3 months, and 6 months. An example application for the Colorado sample (where adult-use, non-medical cannabis legal) is provided which tests the hypothesis that the indirect effect of PNC-txt on reducing cannabis use behavior via changes in attitude differs according to shifts in spatial behavior and consequent change in the activity space exposure to cannabis retailers. Results of moderated mediation modeling support the hypothesis; PNC-txt is significantly more effective when accompanied by shifts in spatial behavior where exposure to cannabis retailers is reduced. Advances in geospatial data and methods have the potential to inform new knowledge regarding the role of social and environmental contextual factors in developing more effective mHealth interventions.

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1 Introduction

The ubiquity and accessibility of location tracking and georeferenced sensing and data collection technologies embedded in mobile phones and other portable devices is revolutionizing research on how an individual's social and physical environmental exposures and interactions shape health [1]. Of particular interest are risky and protective features of the natural, social, economic, and built environments which influence health behaviors and which occur not only within an individual's home neighborhood but also at the routine 'activity space' locations visited throughout daily life [2,3]. Translational spatial information theory research can improve public health through the incorporation of geographic principles into health interventions, programs intended to improve healthy decision-making, typically for behaviors related to chronic diseases, such as substance use disorders (SUDs). This research presents a novel approach for 1) leveraging spatial behavior as a treatment target to advance behavioral 'mobile health' (mHealth) interventions, and 2) capturing and modeling individual activity space and environmental exposure data to investigate mHealth intervention efficacy in the context of a randomized controlled trial (RCT).

As with related advances in mobile and field-based geographic information systems (GIS) [4], mHealth interventions leverage mobile technologies, such as mobile phones, to deliver behavioral interventions. Interventions utilizing mHealth strategies can reduce barriers to access, improve privacy, and support personalization of intervention messaging, providing an effective and scalable approach to improving population health (5). Investigations of mHealth interventions typically focus on questions of whether an intervention is effective (efficacy), how the intervention operates to effect behavioral change (mechanisms), and for whom the intervention is effective (moderation by certain population subgroups). The integration of geospatial data, technologies, and analytical methods in mHealth intervention research represents a substantial research gap recognized in the public health and geography communities [5].

The present research seeks to address this gap by presenting an innovative mHealth SUD intervention which aims to enhance healthy social and spatial behaviors to reduce problematic substance use, as well as a strategy for collecting and modeling longitudinal activity space data to investigate the efficacy and mechanisms of the intervention. To this end, this research describes an RCT of the mHealth SUD intervention PNC-txt (Peer Network Counseling-text). The RCT presented here, funded by the U.S. National Institutes of Health (NIH), tests the efficacy of PNC-txt for reducing problematic cannabis use among young adults with cannabis use disorder (CUD). To the authors' knowledge, with over 1,000 subjects enrolled across the U.S., this program represents the largest ever RCT of an mHealth CUD treatment.

2 The PNC-txt Intervention and Randomized Controlled Trial

The PNC-txt intervention employs Motivational Interviewing [6], a well-known SUD treatment technique which engenders behavioral change by enhancing reflection and consequent action regarding substance use behaviors. PNC-txt focuses on a subject's 'place-based, peer network health,' the environmental exposures associated with the routine day-to-day locations of

the subject's activity space, as well as the social interactions with the subject's close peers that occur at those locations. Healthier choices regarding routine places visited and social interactions are catalyzed through mechanisms which target enhanced awareness, self-efficacy, and protective behavioral strategies. The intervention is delivered via mobile phone text message, including over 160 text messages over a four week period. Messages are customized to each subject based on a baseline assessment of the subject's substance use, spatial behavior, and peer network characteristics. Prior publications provide details on the PNC-txt intervention, including sample text messages [7].

The present PNC-txt RCT enrolled 1,078 young adults primarily via social media platforms. Inclusion criteria were U.S. state of Tennessee or Colorado resident, age 18-25, access to text-capable phone, and evidence of CUD (see [7] for full inclusion and exclusion criteria details). The Institutional Review Board at the University of [SUPRESSED] approved all components of the study. Participants were randomized, stratified by state and sex, to the experimental condition (PNC-txt) or a waitlist control condition. Participants were followed for 6 months, completing a series of assessments via mobile phone at four time points – baseline (at enrollment), 1 month (immediately following completion of the intervention), 3 months past-enrollment, and 6 months post-enrollment. Assessments included survey instruments for substance use behaviors and mental health, as well as the activity space and egocentric social network measures described below. Complete data collection yielded over 1,700 unique measures, for each of the 4 time points, for each of 1,078 subjects.

3 Longitudinal Activity Space Data with Linked Egocentric Social Network Characteristics

Activity space data were collected for each time point using the Ecological Interview (ECO) survey instrument, which asks each subject to list three routine locations they visit throughout the week via a customized interactive map interface delivered via mobile device which zooms in on the subject's home neighborhood and allows the subject to identify activity space locations by pan, zoom, and touch. Once a location is specified, the subject specifies the type of location (e.g. a friend's house), the time of day they typically visit that location (e.g. weekends, evenings), how often, how they travel there, and their feelings of stress and safety at that location, among other attributes.

Egocentric social network data were collected for each time point using the Young Adult Social Network Assessment (YASNA) survey instrument. The YASNA asks each subject to list three close friends and, for each friend, their cannabis use behaviors, influence on the subject to use cannabis, and level of social supports, yielding a set of three friend-specific peer network health scores, as well as a subject-level summary peer network health score, for each time point. The subject also names, who, among the three friends, spends time with them at each activity space location, thus providing longitudinal, linked activity space-egocentric social network data for each subject, where data on key place-based perceptions and behaviors unique to each subject are collected.

Figure 1 illustrates, diagrammatically, the linked activity space-egocentric social network data collection for a single subject over the four time points, where the blue point is the subject's home and the red points are the subject's activity space locations (from the ECO), where each location can be associated with up to three friends (from the YASNA). For instance, Figure 1 shows that at baseline the subject spends time at activity space location #1 with friend #2 and at location #2 with friends #1 and #3. At 1 month, activity space location #2 has shifted to a different location, and a new friend #3 has been identified and

■ **Figure 1** Figure 1. Illustration of how longitudinal, linked activity space (Ecological Interview [ECO]) and egocentric social network (Young Adult Social Network Assessment [YASNA]) data are collected for one subject over four time points – at baseline and 1, 3, and 6 months. A map is shown for each time point, at each of which data are collected on the subject’s home location (blue point), the locations of three activity space locations (red points), and three friends (silhouettes). Each activity space location is associated with up to three friends. See text for further explanation.

associated with that location. At 3 months, the subject moves to a different home location, and 6 months, activity space location #3 has changed to a different location and a new friend # 1 is associated with that location.

Note that by associating friends with activity space locations, the approach yields place-based, egocentric social network measures, such as the peer influence to use cannabis, not only for each subject, but also for each activity space location unique to each subject, over time. In addition, home and activity space locations at each time point may be linked to external GIS data capturing features of the natural, built, and socioeconomic environment based on relationships of spatial coincidence, proximity, and density, such as measures of neighborhood deprivation by U.S. Census tract or proximity to locations of cannabis retailers (in Colorado). This data capture approach thus supports the integration of dynamic place-based, social interaction and environmental exposure measures into models of whether PNC-txt works to reduce cannabis use (i.e. efficacy), how PNC-txt treatment works (i.e. mechanisms), and for whom.

4 Motivating Example: Modeling the Impact of Activity Space Change on a Mechanism of PNC-txt Efficacy

Here, a motivating example is provided that demonstrates how the longitudinal activity space data can be integrated into models of mechanisms of PNC-txt efficacy, with a focus on the effect of activity space exposure to cannabis retailers. The analysis is, therefore, restricted to the subset of subjects residing in Colorado, where adult-use, non-medical cannabis retail sales are legal, and who have complete data for the analysis ($N=422$).

Previous research indicates that PNC-txt indirectly reduces the number of days a subject used cannabis in the past 30-days via ‘readiness to change,’ a key clinical mediating mechanism for behavioral health interventions related to self-efficacy, where subjects are theorized to proceed through stages of change regarding their substance use, beginning with stage 1, ‘I enjoy using and will never change,’ and proceeding to stage 10, ‘I made a change and will not use as I did before.’ Readiness to change was measured at each time point using the validated survey instrument The Marijuana Ladder [8].

■ **Figure 2** Figure 2. Diagrammatic model of the indirect effect of PNC-txt on past 30-day cannabis use via the mediator readiness to change, as moderated by activity space exposure to cannabis retailers.

Prior research on an mHealth tobacco use intervention indicates that readiness to change and intervention efficacy are influenced by exposure to tobacco retailers, as measured by retailer density [9], as passive exposure to tobacco sales and advertising can influence tobacco craving and thus suppress intervention effects. The present research hypothesizes an analogous model in the context of CUD treatment, where the indirect effect of PNC-txt on reducing past 30-day cannabis use (change from baseline to 6 months) through readiness to change (change from baseline to 1 month, at the conclusion of the intervention) is moderated by exposure to cannabis retailers (change from baseline to 3 months). Thus, the model captures the cascading chronological effects of treatment on attitudes and consequently on cannabis use, with intervening effects of changes in spatial behavior. Exposure to cannabis retailers at each time point is measured by the mean number of cannabis retailers within 1 mile of the three activity space locations.

Figure 2 presents a conceptual diagram of the model. Note that baseline values of readiness to change, past 30-day cannabis use, and exposure to cannabis retailers are included in the model to capture change over time, as is the moderation by exposure to cannabis retailers on the direct effect of PNC-txt on the outcome. It is expected that the indirect treatment effect of PNC-txt will be stronger for subjects who reduce their exposure to cannabis retailers, as compared to subjects who do not reduce their exposure, by enhancing the effect of readiness to change on reductions in cannabis use. The model is implemented in a moderated mediation regression model using PROCESS v4.2 [10] implemented in SPSS v28.0.1.0 (IBM, Inc.) with 10,000 bootstrap samples and a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$. Variables forming the moderators are mean-centered.

Results indicate that the hypothesis is supported; the indirect effect of PNC-txt on reductions in past 30-day cannabis use via readiness to change is moderated by exposure to cannabis retailers. The indirect effect of PNC-txt on reducing past 30-day cannabis use via readiness to change occurs only when exposure to cannabis retailers is below the mean ($= -0.848$, 95% CI -1.543 , -0.305) or at the mean ($= -0.581$, 95% CI -1.110 , -0.153), but not when above the mean ($= -0.247$, 95% CI: -0.782 , 0.271). These results are illustrated graphically in Figure 3, where differences in the association between readiness to change and past 30-day cannabis use are shown for different levels of exposure to cannabis retailers, where steeper slopes indicate stronger effects. Though preliminary, these results provide potential evidence that the efficacy of PNC-txt to reduce cannabis use via readiness to change differs according to changes in spatial behavior and consequent shifts in activity space exposure to cannabis retailers.

5 Conclusion

This paper contributes to spatial information theory by advancing translational research for 1) leveraging spatial behavior as a treatment target in a behavioral mHealth intervention, and 2) measuring and modeling longitudinal activity space data for investigating treatment efficacy and mechanisms within an RCT. Advances in geospatial data and methods have the potential to inform new knowledge regarding the role of social and environmental contextual factors in developing more effective mHealth interventions.

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■ **Figure 3** Figure 3. The effect of readiness to change at 1 month (controlling for baseline value) on past 30-day cannabis use at 6 months (controlling for baseline value), at different levels of exposure to cannabis retailers at 3 months (controlling for baseline value) – one standard deviation below the mean level of exposure, at the mean, and one standard deviation above the mean. Steeper slopes indicate stronger effects.